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OPPORTUNITIES IN INDIAN MARKET OF MUTUAL FUNDS INVESTMENT

Dr. Rajesh Kumar ¹

Mr. Nitin Goel ²

¹Associate Professor-cum-Head (P.G. Deptt. Of Commerce)

Address: K.L.S.D College, Ludhiana (Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh)

² Assistant Professor (P.G.Deptt. Of Commerce)

Address: K.L.S.D College, Ludhiana (Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh)

Abstract

Household savings play an important role in domestic capital formation. Only a small part of the household savings in India is channelized to the capital market. Attracting more household savings to the capital market requires efficient intermediation. Mutual funds have emerged as one of the important class of financial intermediaries which cater to the needs of retail investors. Mutual funds have become an important vehicle for mobilization of savings particularly from the household sector. Mutual funds are one of the most favoured investment routes for the small and medium investors across the world. Ideally, Mutual funds provide opportunities for small investors to participate in the capital market without assuming a very high degree of risk. An important principle of investment in capital market is that do not put all the eggs in one basket i.e. diversification. A small investor is not able to have a diversified portfolio mainly due to paucity of resources. However, a mutual fund pools together the savings of such small investors and invests the same in the capital market and passes the benefits to the investors. Thus, investors can indirectly participate in the capital market by subscribing to the units of mutual funds. Mutual funds employ professional fund managers to manage the investment activities. Therefore, investors also get benefits of professional expertise of these managers.

Keywords: Behavior, Investors' Perception, Mutual Fund, Performance and Preferences

INTRODUCTION

This Consumer behaviour from the marketing world and financial economics have come together to bring to surface an exciting area for study and research in the form of Behavioural Finance and it has been gaining importance over the recent years. With reforms in financial sector and the developments in the Indian financial markets, Mutual Funds (MFs) have emerged to be an important investment avenue for retail (small) investors. The investment habit of the small investors

¹ Associate Professor & Head, P.G. Dept. of Commerce & Mgt., Kamla Lohtia S.D. College, Ludhiana

² Assistant Professor, P.G. Dept. of Commerce & Mgt., Kamla Lohtia S.D. College, Ludhiana

particularly has undergone a sea change. Increasing number of players from public as well as private sectors has entered in to the market with innovative schemes to cater to the requirements of the investors in India and abroad. For all investors, particularly the small investors, mutual funds have provided a better alternative to obtain benefits of expertise- based equity investments to all types of investors. So in this scenario where many schemes are flooded in to market, it is important to analyse needs of consumers and to find out which factors affects consumers' needs the most.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Panda and Tripathy (2001) in their paper aimed to track investors' preferences and priorities towards different types of mutual fund products. The study concluded that while designing a mutual fund product the fund manager has to be concerned about offering a mix of combination in risk, return and liquidity. The main factors affecting the decision of an investor have been notified as; core expectations, tangible product, service behaviour, persuasive communication and confidence factor.

Ahmad, Nazir (2002) in his paper examined the empirical evidence with regard to investors' perceptions towards mutual funds operating in public and private sectors in the cities of Srinagar and Jammu. The paper analysed mutual funds for six focus areas such as asset prioritization, product preference, motivating factors, fund expectations, capital market; investor skepticism by selecting respondents from five service classes, viz. education, medicine, law, banks and insurance. The paper concluded that the officers working in banks and financial institution were more conscious and aware about mutual funds than other service classes.

Panwar and Madhumathi (2006) in their study identified the differences in characteristics of public-sector and private-sector sponsored mutual funds and found the extent of diversification in the portfolio of securities of public-sector and private-sector sponsored mutual funds and compared their performance using traditional investment measures. The study found that public-sector sponsored, private-sector Indian sponsored, and private-sector foreign sponsored mutual funds did not differ statistically in terms of portfolio characteristics such as net assets, common stock percent, market capitalization.

Selvam and Palanisamy (2011) studied the risk and return relationship of Indian mutual fund schemes. The study found out that out of 35 sample schemes, 11 showed significant t-values and the other 24 sample schemes did not prove to have significant relationship between the risk and returns. According to t-alpha values, the majority of (32) of the sample schemes' returns were not significantly different from market returns, and very few number of sample schemes' returns were significantly different from their market returns during the study period.

Rao and Daita (2013) in their study attempted to analyze the influence of fundamental factors such as economy, industry, and company on the performance of mutual funds. Efforts was made to carry out an in-depth analysis of the economy through a collection of monthly data pertaining to key macro-economic variables covering a period of 228 months spread over 19 years. The casual relationship between real economic variables and their impact on statistics, correlation matrix, and Granger's causality test. To appraise the mutual fund industry various aspects such as assets under management, investor type, and product classification were studied with the help of percentage analysis.

Sundar and Prakash (2014) in their study examined the awareness among the investor community in choosing the best mutual fund scheme as it conducted a comparative analysis of the mutual funds of three AMCs. This study also showed that much information about mutual funds is not available publicly. There is no information on fund styles or comprehensive league tables to allow the comparison of mutual funds in the market. This study introduced a method which examines the relation between fund returns and fund asset size, cash holding, loads, expense ratio, and turnover.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- Method used for evaluating the performance of mutual funds
- Investors’ perception regarding benefits offered
- Sources of information relied upon by investors
- Investors’ perception towards mutual funds
- Investors’ perception about future prospect of mutual fund industry
- Idea about future investment of investors

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Investor’s main objective is to earn higher returns keeping in mind the risk and liquidity factor. With this objective in mind, an investor is looking out for various investment avenues. Mutual funds offer comparatively better returns and have less risk as compared to direct investment in stock market. In this research paper, an attempt has been made to evaluate the perception of investors regarding mutual fund investment.

A survey was conducted in Ludhiana during the period April 2013 to April 2014. Samples of 150 individual mutual fund investors were surveyed through a pre-tested questionnaire. The investors were selected on the basis of those who have made prior investment in mutual funds and have some knowledge about the basic terminologies involved with mutual funds. An attempt has been made to find out the perception of investors regarding mutual fund investment and to identify the factors considered to be important by the investors before investing in any mutual fund. The analysis of primary data collected through opinionistic survey of investors has been made by making use of statistical tools like tabulation, percentage, ranking and scoring, weighted average score, Kendall’s coefficient of concordance etc.

ANALYSIS & DISCUSSIONS

1. Basis for Performance Evaluation

Basis used for performance evaluation by different investors depends upon their knowledge of market, their ability to evaluate market and the time they can devote to analyse the performance of schemes. Every investor evaluates performance of mutual fund schemes before and after making investment in mutual funds. Various performance evaluation measures have been used for this purpose. The investors either evaluate the trend by taking absolute return of the scheme or they can compare the performance of particular scheme with that of other schemes of same mutual funds or schemes of similar nature. Even evaluation of a particular scheme can be made on the basis of risk-adjusted return of that scheme.

TABLE 1
Basis used for Performance Evaluation

Basis	Number of investors	Percentage of investors
Absolute Return	96	48.00
Fund Return Vs Market Return	46	23.00
Fund Return Vs Return on Similar Schemes	35	17.50
Risk Adjusted Return	23	11.50
TOTAL	200	100.00

A look at the table 1 reveals that maximum number of investors 48% have used only absolute returns for evaluating performance of mutual funds followed by 23% investors who compared returns of schemes with market return and least number of investor 11.5% have used risk adjusted returns for evaluating the performance of mutual fund schemes.

2. Investors’ Perception About Benefits Offered

The main benefits considered by investors in mutual funds are Return, Safety, Liquidity and Diversification. The views of he Investors have been taken regarding such benefits offered by mutual funds and these have been ranked on a five-point scale.

TABLE 2
Opinion of Investors Regarding Benefits Offered

Benefits	Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Very Low	WAS*	Ranks**
Return	28	116	37	13	6	49.80	II
Safety	23	101	34	35	7	46.53	IV
Liquidity	62	92	33	10	3	53.33	I
Diversification	55	63	53	22	7	49.13	III

The highest weighted average score 53.33 in the above table proves that liquidity has been the first preference of investors. Return and diversification have been given second and third preference respectively by investors while safety has got least preference.

3. Sources Relied Upon by Investors for Getting Information While Investing

Ignorance may be bliss in the realm of literature but it may lead to disastrous consequences in matters of financial nature. Needless to say, the timely and right type of information leads to right investment decisions and gainful results. Investors require information not only for subscribing to new schemes of mutual funds but also for evaluating the performance of existing schemes. The investment decisions of uninformed or ill-informed investors are based more on instinct than on sound and prudent judgment and hence can't be considered rational and reliable. Thus, the importance of adequate and dependable information for investment decisions can hardly be over emphasized.

Generally, most of the investors do not invest on their own in a particular mutual fund. They may either be influenced by prospectus/newsletters/advertisements or persuaded by their financial experts/brokers/sub brokers and friend/relatives. These sources fulfil the varying requirements of the investors and different investors have different preferences so far as these sources of information are concerned. In the following table an attempt has been made to analyse the impact of different sources of information on decision-making by the investors.

TABLE 3
Preferences towards Different Sources of Information

Sources Relied Upon	1	2	3	4	5	WAS*	Ranks**
Broker/Sub-broker	53	57	46	28	16	46.87	II
Prospectus/Newsletter	62	51	56	22	9	49.00	I
Friends/Relatives	23	28	56	57	36	36.33	IV
Professional Magazines/ Newspapers	55	45	29	61	10	44.93	III
Advertisements	7	19	13	32	129	22.87	V

Note: (1) *Weights equal to 5,4,3,2,1 have been assigned to Rank 1,2,3,4,5 respectively to calculate weighted average score.

(2) **WAS has been assigned ranks in the descending order.

Table 3 exhibits the ranks and weighted average scores obtained by different sources relied upon by investors. It is clear from the table that prospectus/newsletters having WAS at 49 have been considered as the most important source of information by investors followed by brokers/sub brokers, professional magazines/ newspapers, and friends/relatives. On the other hand, advertisement had the least influence on the decisions of investors for making investment in mutual funds as WAS for the same has been very low, that is , 22.87.

4. Investors' Perception Toward Mutual Funds

Many Public and Private sector mutual funds have been operating in India. Some people prefer to invest in private sector mutual funds while others in public sector mutual funds. An effort has been made to see the preferences of investors regarding mutual funds selected for the study.

TABLE 4
Investors' Preferences Regarding Mutual Fund

Table 4 exhibits the rank assigned by investors to different mutual funds. After analyzing the table it is clear that Franklin Templeton Mutual Fund has been the most preferred mutual fund as it got highest weighted average score of 25.59 followed by 23.45 in case of Prudential ICICI Mutual Fund and 23.44 in case of HDFC Mutual Fund. Birla Sunlife Mutual Fund has got fourth position. On the other hand, among the least preferred mutual funds GIC Mutual Fund has got 12th position preceded by Canbank Mutual Fund at 11th position and Alliance Mutual Fund at 10th position. It is interesting to note that the topmost positions have been held by private sector mutual funds whereas all the bottom positions have gone to public sector mutual funds.

Preference	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	WAS*	RANKS**
LIC MF	1	4	16	13	29	30	23	28	15	16	13	12	15.37	VIII
GIC MF	-	-	1	2	10	9	14	12	14	25	57	56	8.21	XII
SBI MF	11	16	10	11	21	23	26	23	21	22	13	3	16.49	V
CANBANK MF	1	1	2	12	8	4	10	11	12	14	47	78	7.95	XI
HDFC MF	30	44	24	38	22	15	6	7	10	3	-	1	23.44	III
PRINCIPAL MF	12	16	12	4	12	17	37	37	17	21	7	8	16.04	VII
FRANKLIN TEMPLETON MF	77	31	29	13	9	8	7	6	5	5	9	1	25.59	I
RELIANCE MF	20	9	10	10	17	28	22	23	27	17	10	10	16.21	VI
BIRLA SUNLIFE MF	12	33	36	44	16	16	7	5	15	10	4	2	21.41	IV
ALLIANCE MF	3	5	5	7	7	12	10	22	40	54	24	11	9.26	X
TATA MF	3	3	9	12	38	29	31	24	18	10	11	12	15.59	IX
PRUDENTIAL ICICI MF	30	41	46	34	11	9	7	2	6	3	5	6	23.45	II

5. Investors' Perception About Future Prospect of Mutual Fund Industry

In the face of fast changing financial environment both at domestic and global level, it is not easier to make predictions about the future of mutual fund industry, yet the investors' belief in this respect can be expected to offer a reasonable direction. Accordingly, an endeavour has been made to obtain appropriate responses about the prospects of mutual funds in India. The responses in this connection have been generated at a five point scale used for the purpose. The investors were asked to put a tick mark against any of the 5 alternatives responses: very bright, bright, can't say, bleak and very bleak. The responses, obtained separately for private and public sector mutual funds, are organized at the overall level.

TABLE 5
Investors Opinion regarding Future of Mutual Funds

Category	Very Bright	Bright	Can't Say	Bleak	Very Bleak	Total
Public Sector	14(7.00)	110(55.00)	55(27.50)	18(9.00)	3(1.50)	200
Private Sector	106(53.00)	69(34.50)	18(9.00)	7(3.50)	-	200
Total	120(30.00)	179(44.75)	73(18.25)	25(6.25)	3(0.75)	400

Note: Figures in parentheses denote percentage with total

A look at Table 5 makes it clear that at the overall level 30% and 44.75% of investors viewed very bright and bright future respectively. On the other hand, bleak and very bleak future has been expected by 6.25% and .75% of investors respectively.

The table further shows that the percentage of investors who expressed their inability in giving a comment about the prospects of mutual funds stood at 18.25% at the overall level. As regards public sector only 7% of investors expected very bright future as compared to 53% in case of private sector. Bright future has been expected by 55% of investors in case of public sector as compared to 34.5% in case of private sector. 1.5% and 9% of investors viewed very bleak and bleak future of public sector mutual funds as compared to none and 3.5% in case of private sector respectively.

6. Sector-Wise Preferences of Investors Regarding Future Investment

The popularity of private sector mutual funds has been increasing day-by-day since their inception in 1993 as this account now for more than 70% of total resources mobilized by mutual funds. Opinion of mutual fund investors has been sought regarding their sector-wise future investment.

TABLE 6
Sector-wise Pattern of Future Investment in Mutual Fund

Category	Number of Investors	Percentage of Investors
Public	15	7.5
Private	177	88.5
Both	4	2.0
Not Interested	4	2.0
Total	200	100

Note: Figures in parentheses denote percentage with total

A look at table reveals that maximum percentage of investors 88.5% has been interested in making investment in future in private sector mutual funds. Only 7.5% of them are interested in public sector mutual funds whereas 88.5% of them want to invest in private sector in future. A very thin percentage of investors 2% do not want to invest in mutual fund in future.

7. Category-Wise Preferences Regarding Future Investment

There has been a plethora of schemes offered by mutual funds to its investors. Investors depending upon their investment objective can make investment in various kinds of schemes. An attempt has been made have to see the popularity of various schemes among mutual fund schemes.

TABLE 7
Category-wise Pattern of Future Investment in Mutual Fund

Category	Number of Investors	Percentage of Investors
Growth Schemes	74	37.00
Balanced Schemes	6	3.00
Tax Saving Schemes	6	3.00
Diversified Schemes	46	23.00
Index Schemes	-	0.00
Income Schemes	4	2.00

More than One Scheme	60	30.00
Not Interested	4	2.00
Total	200	100.00

Note: Figures in parentheses denote percentage with total

Table 7 exhibits that maximum percentage of investors 37% want to invest in growth schemes followed by investors 30% who want to make investment in more than one scheme. Diversified schemes occupy third place as 23% of investors want to make their investment in them. Income schemes have been least preferred as only 2% of investors want to make their investment in them while 3% of investors have been interested in balanced and tax saving schemes of mutual funds in future.

CONCLUSION

Majority of investors have used absolute return on the mutual fund scheme as the basis for evaluating their performance. As regards the benefits offered by mutual funds, investors have placed liquidity at number one followed by return, diversification and safety in order. Most of the investors relied on past performance of the mutual funds while making investment in that mutual fund. Prospectus/Newsletters have been the most important source used by the investors while making investment followed by brokers and sub-brokers. Franklin Templeton Mutual Fund has been the most preferred mutual fund followed by Prudential ICICI Mutual Fund and HDFC Mutual Fund. A very bright future has been expected of private sector mutual fund industry as against bright future expected of public sector. Maximum percentage of investors has been interested in making investment in future in private sector mutual funds. Maximum percentage of investors wants to invest in growth schemes followed by investors who want to make investment in more than one scheme. Diversified schemes occupy third place.

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